

EXPLORING THE IMPACT OF AGE AND WEIGHT ON SLEEP QUALITY: INSIGHTS FROM THE URBANOME PROJECT

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Introduction

Sleep is considered to play an important role in cognitive and physiological functions in humans. Poor sleep quality has been studied as a risk factor for weight gain [1]. Furthermore, the quality of sleep has been found to decrease with healthy aging [2]. The objective of the present analysis is to evaluate the relationship between sleep quality, age and weight, utilizing data acquired for the interventional study in Thessaloniki as part of the URBANOME Horizon 2020 project.

Materials and methods

A custom risk-scoring methodology identified 121 high-risk volunteers to be included in this analysis based on pneumological exams and a survey regarding Sleep Quality, Quality of Life, Mental Health, Physical Health and Urban Environment, Housing, and Personal Habits. Participants were provided with a Xiaomi Smart Band 7 and a portable sensor to measure particulate matter (PM), humidity and temperature. They were instructed to wear these sensors for 1 week to monitor activity, sleep quality and exposure to environmental factors. The objective was to evaluate the relationship between sleep quality and demographics using two-way ANOVA to analyze weekly durations of light, deep, and REM sleep, as well as wake time.

Results

The tests confirmed that the data followed a normal distribution (Table 1). A statistically significant interaction was observed between sleep stage, weight, and age (p-value = 0.03). As shown in Figure 1, the deep sleep ratio increases with age among participants with lower weight (adjusted p-value = 0.04).

Table 1: Normality test results.

Data subset	p-value
Older & overweight	0.17
Young & overweight	0.25
Older & normal weight	0.11
Young & normal weight	0.98

Figure 1: Weekly deep sleep ratio by age and weight.

Discussion

The analysis suggests that older adults tend to have a higher deep sleep ratio than younger individuals, while weight affects deep sleep in both age groups, with higher-weighted older adults having a lower deep sleep ratio than lower-weighted, while the opposite effect is noted in younger participants.

Conclusions

The findings of this analysis provide valuable insights into the relationship between sleep quality, age, and weight, highlighting the importance of good physiology to maintain sleep quality across lifespan. Targeted interventions, such as promoting weight management and optimizing sleep environments, could be tailored by age group to enhance sleep quality, offering valuable guidance for urban health policy and personalized public health strategies.

References

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